

BLOOM DELIVERABLE D12.2

D12.2 – DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN UPDATE P1 (DMP P1)

Summary:

This deliverable outlines the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the BLOOM project, structured in alignment with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and Horizon Europe's Open Science guidelines. It defines procedures for the generation, documentation, storage, access, and preservation of data produced by the consortium. The plan specifies governance roles, version control mechanisms, metadata standards, and recommended licensing models. It distinguishes between open and restricted data, ensuring the protection of sensitive information and full GDPR compliance. Trusted repositories such as Zenodo, GitHub, and UPC's institutional archive are used for publication and long-term preservation. The DMP is a living document, subject to periodic updates (M6, M19, M37) and internal validation. This strategy ensures traceability, sustainability, and the scientific impact of BLOOM's research outputs.

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